

Some new organotin(IV) complexes of biologically important semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones

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Abstract : The present paper is a report on the synthesis of some new organotin(IV) complexes by the reactions of bis(tributyltin)oxide and semicarbazones/thiosemicarbazones using benzene as reaction medium. Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones are prepared by condensation of 4-acetylbiphenyl, 2-acetylfluorene, 9-acetylanthracene, anthraldehyde and 4-fluoro-acetophenone with semicarbazide hydrochloride and thiosemicarbazide in ethanol. Monomeric nature of these complexes has been confirmed on the basis of their molecular weight determination. Purity of the complexes has been confirmed by thin layer chromatography. Non electrolytic nature of complexes has been detected by their conductance measurement. The bonding pattern and geometry of tin complexes are characterized by spectroscopic studies (IR, UV, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, ^{119}Sn NMR, spectral studies). The investigated compounds and the ligands were tested against bacterial and fungal species. The bacteria and fungi used in these investigations are *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Bacillus thurengiensis* (bacteria) and *F. oxysporum*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *R. phaseoli* (fungi). The metal complexes have higher activity than the free ligands.

Keywords : Organotin(IV) complexes, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, spectral studies, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

On account of their pronounced biological activities, semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones are considered the most important nitrogen-oxygen/sulphur donor ligands in coordination chemistry¹. Both of them act as neutral or charged ligand moieties^{2,3}.

The real impetus towards developing the coordination chemistry of these potential ligands were probably provided by the remarkable antitumor, antiviral and antimalarial activity⁴ observed for some of these derivatives, which has been shown to be related to their metal complexing ability. A few α -(*N*)-heterocyclic carboxy-aldehyde thiosemicarbazones and their complexes possess antitumor activity^{6,7}. It is also reported that anticancer activity in certain ligands increases by its coordination to tin metal⁸.

The biological activity of metal coordination compounds derived from semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones has led to considerable interest in their coordination chemistry due to their interesting stereochemistry as only the β -nitrogen coordinated to the metal atom. The rapid rise in the industrial, agricultural and medical ap-

plication of organotin(IV) compounds⁹ during the last few decades have led to their accumulation in the environment and in biological systems¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

Our continuing interest in chelated organotin compounds has led us to synthesize some tin derivatives of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones, usually bind to a metal ion as bidentate N, S donor ligands¹⁵. Many organotin(IV) complexes with semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones present an interesting variety of structural possibilities. This aspect has been attracting the attention of a number of researchers and a multitude of structural types have been discovered. Both aliphatic and aromatic semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones in their neutral and deprotonated forms have been used to react with bis(tributyltin)oxide. The complexes formed exhibit variable stoichiometry in the metal to ligand ratio and different mode of coordination¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

It is demonstrated earlier that semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones ligands have enzyme inhibiting properties. The tuberculostic properties of semicarbazides/thiosemicarbazides and their condensation products with different carbonyl compounds are known to be less toxic

than the parent one, this is probably due to the blocking of the free amino group¹⁹⁻²⁹.

The ligands used in present investigation are shown as in Fig. 1 semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones of 4-acetyl biphenyl (a), 2-acetyl fluorene (b), 9-acetyl anthracene (c), anthraldehyde (d) and 4-fluoro-acetophenone (e).

where X = O or S
(O = semicarbazones)
(S = thiosemicarbazones)

Fig. 1. Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones used as ligands in this work.

Therefore, the present paper describes structural characterization of some new coordination compounds of tin(IV) with semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones. These complexes have a long history and broad spectrum of biological efficacy that includes antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

The reaction of bis(tributyltin)oxide with these ligands have been carried out in 1 : 2 molar ratio in refluxing benzene. These proceed with the liberation of water, which is removed azeotropically with benzene.

The above reactions were found to be quite facile and could be completed in 6–10 h of refluxing. The resulting complexes (Table 2) are obtained in the form of solid and semisolids. These are monomeric, low melting solids are

Table 1. Analytical and physical properties of ligands

Ligands	Colour and State	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
			C	H	N	O	S	F	
4-Acetyl biphenyl semicarbazone (L ¹ H) (C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O)	Yellow solid	240d	70.98 (71.12)	5.11 (5.96)	16.11 (16.58)	6.03 (6.31)	-	-	252.90 (253.28)
4-Acetyl biphenyl thiosemicarbazone (L ² H) (C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ S)	White solid	180	66.76 (66.88)	5.28 (5.61)	15.45 (15.60)	-	11.00 (11.90)	-	269.06 (269.34)
2-Acetyl fluorene semicarbazone (L ³ H) (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O)	Pale yellow shiny	220	74.08 (74.43)	5.68 (5.69)	15.71 (15.83)	5.96 (6.03)	-	-	264.97 (265.29)
2-Acetyl fluorene thiosemicarbazone (L ⁴ H) (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S)	Yellow powder	165	67.96 (68.29)	5.01 (5.37)	14.86 (14.93)	-	11.39 (11.55)	-	281.30 (281.35)
9-Acetyl anthracene semicarbazone (L ⁵ H) (C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O)	Orange shiny	220	73.26 (73.62)	5.21 (5.45)	15.08 (15.15)	5.45 (5.76)	-	-	277.20 (277.30)
9-Acetyl anthracene thiosemicarbazone (L ⁶ H) (C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ S)	Yellowish orange	145	69.40 (69.59)	5.08 (5.15)	14.98 (14.32)	-	10.92 (10.98)	-	293.06 (293.56)
Anthraldehyde semicarbazone (L ⁷ H) (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O)	Orange	245	72.90 (72.98)	4.86 (4.97)	15.75 (15.95)	5.96 (6.07)	-	-	263.20 (263.28)
Anthraldehyde thiosemicarbazone (L ⁸ H) (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S)	Yellow	140	68.05 (68.79)	4.61 (4.69)	15.00 (15.04)	-	11.47 (11.80)	-	279.16 (279.34)
4-Fluoro acetophenone semicarbazone (L ⁹ H) (C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₃ OF)	White	205	55.00 (55.37)	5.04 (5.16)	21.06 (21.52)	7.95 (8.19)	-	9.73 (9.88)	195.00 (195.18)
4-Fluoro acetophenone thiosemicarbazone (L ¹⁰ H) (C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₃ SF)	White crystal	114	51.11 (51.16)	4.46 (4.77)	19.06 (19.89)	-	15.17 (15.45)	8.99 (9.03)	211.11 (211.24)

Table 2. Some new coordination compounds of bis(tributyltin)oxide with semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones

Reactant	Ligand	Molar ratio	Yield (%)	Product	Colour and State	M.p. (°C)	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
								Sn	N	S
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{15}H_{15}N_3O)(L^1H)$	1 : 2	78	$(C_{15}H_{14}N_3O)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Yellow	290	542.03 (542.60)	25.95 (26.04)	9.16 (9.19)	-
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{15}H_{15}N_3S)(L^2H)$	1 : 2	74	$(C_{15}H_{14}N_3S)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Cream	200d	558.08 (558.66)	25.04 (25.15)	8.76 (8.88)	6.68 (6.77)
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{16}H_{15}N_3O)(L^3H)$	1 : 2	72	$(C_{16}H_{14}N_3O)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Brown	240	554.09 (554.61)	25.06 (25.37)	8.48 (8.96)	-
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{16}H_{15}N_3S)(L^4H)$	1 : 2	76	$(C_{16}H_{14}N_3S)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Yellow	170	570.40 (570.71)	24.46 (24.53)	8.46 (8.66)	6.48 (6.61)
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{17}H_{15}N_3O)(L^5H)$	1 : 2	74	$(C_{17}H_{14}N_3O)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Orange	240	566.09 (566.62)	24.39 (24.74)	8.66 (8.73)	-
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{17}H_{15}N_3S)(L^6H)$	1 : 2	73	$(C_{17}H_{14}N_3O)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Yellowish orange	160	582.60 (582.68)	23.48 (23.94)	8.04 (8.45)	6.35 (6.45)
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{16}H_{13}N_3O)(L^7H)$	1 : 2	77	$(C_{16}H_{12}N_3O)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Yellow	250	552.00 (552.60)	24.99 (25.48)	8.89 (8.99)	-
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_{16}H_{13}N_3S)(L^8H)$	1 : 2	71	$(C_{16}H_{12}N_3S)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	Orange	150	568.52 (568.66)	24.08 (24.63)	8.09 (8.69)	6.60 (6.63)
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_9H_{10}N_3OF)(L^9H)$	1 : 2	79	$(C_{16}H_{12}N_3O)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	White	210	484.48 (484.50)	29.49 (29.83)	10.45 (10.53)	-
$[(C_4H_9)_3Sn]_2O$	$(C_9H_{10}N_3SF)(L^{10}H)$	1 : 2	73	$(C_{16}H_{12}N_3S)$ $(C_4H_9)_3Sn$	White	150	499.39 (499.43)	28.46 (28.68)	10.06 (10.12)	7.65 (7.72)

C and H analysis are found satisfactory.

Table 3. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones and their tin(IV) complexes

Compd.	v(N-H) or v(OH)	v(C=N)	v(Sn-O)	v(Sn-N)	v(Sn-S)
(L ¹ H)	3240	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₇ H ₄₁ N ₃ OSn)	-	1630	680, 620	500, 400	320, 300
(L ² H)	3250	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₇ H ₄₁ N ₃ SSn)	-	1620	720, 690	420, 410	320, 300
(L ³ H)	3240	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₈ H ₄₁ N ₃ OSn)	-	1610	750, 680	450, 420	400, 340
(L ⁴ H)	3340	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₈ H ₄₁ N ₃ SSn)	-	1620	720, 700	420, 400	410, 370
(L ⁵ H)	3240	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₉ H ₄₁ N ₃ OSn)	-	1610	690, 620	400, 390	350, 320
(L ⁶ H)	3340	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₉ H ₄₁ N ₃ SSn)	-	1618	720, 680	425, 415	320, 310
(L ⁷ H)	3260	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₈ H ₃₉ N ₃ OSn)	-	1650	680, 620	450, 420	320, 302
(L ⁸ H)	3220	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₈ H ₃₉ N ₃ SSn)	-	1610	680, 615	420, 400	325, 315
(L ⁹ H)	3240	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₁ H ₃₆ N ₃ OSnF)	-	1620	670, 620	450, 410	410, 340
(L ¹⁰ H)	3340	-	-	-	-
(C ₂₁ H ₃₆ N ₃ SSF)	-	1618	660, 630	460, 420	320, 310

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

A very important property of ¹¹⁹Sn NMR is that the corresponding chemical shift is strongly dependent on the coordination number of tin atom. The compound 4-acetyl biphenyl semicarbazono tributyl tin(IV) gives a sharp ¹¹⁹Sn signal in the NMR spectrum at δ 260 ppm and which is in accordance with the proposed five-coordinated structure as reported earlier also. On the basis of the foregoing discussion the following tentative structures may be assigned to these complexes. The data are given in Table 4.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antifungal activity of the ligands and their complexes with tin complexes has been evaluated by Radial Growth Method³⁶ using Czapek's agar medium having the composition, glucose 20 g, starch 20 g, agar-agar 20 g and distil water 1000 ml. To this medium was added requisite amount of the compound after being dissolved in dimethylformamide so as to get a certain final concentration (50, 100 and 200 ppm). The medium was then poured into the petri plates and the spores of fungi were placed on the medium with the help of an inoculum needle.

Table 4. Nuclear magnetic resonance data for semicarbazones/thiosemicarbazones and the corresponding tin complexes in δ ppm

Compd.	H-C=N	¹¹⁹ Sn NMR	NH	Aromatic protons
L ¹ H	8.25	-	10.22	7.90-6.80
(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O)(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn	9.25	260	-	7.95-6.79
(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ S)(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn	8.60	268	-	6.08-6.00
L ² H	8.08	-	10.21	7.77-7.15
(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ O)(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn	9.25	255	-	7.72-7.15
(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ S)(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn	9.22	260	-	7.80-7.20
L ³ H	8.26	-	10.33	7.90-7.15
(C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O)(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn	9.00	255	-	7.22-7.00
(C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ S)(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn	9.06	265	-	6.90-6.22

These petri plates were wrapped in polythene bags containing a few drops of alcohol and were placed in an incubator at 30 ± 1 °C. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the fungal colony diameter after four days. The percentage inhibition was calculated as $100(C - T)/C$, where C and T are the diameters of the fungus colony in the control and test plates, respectively. The fungi used in these investigations included *F. oxysporum*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger* and *R. phaseoli*.

The activity against bacteria was evaluated by the Inhibition Zone Technique³⁷. The nutrient agar medium having the composition peptone 5 g, beef extract 5 g, NaCl 5 g, agar-agar 20 g and distil water 1000 ml was pipeted into the petri plates³⁸. When it solidified, 5 ml of warm seeded agar was applied. The seeded agar was prepared by cooling the molten agar to 40 °C and then added the amount of bacterial suspension. The compounds were dissolved in dimethyl formamide in 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations. Paper discs of Whatman No. 1 filter paper measuring diameter of 5 mm were soaked in these solutions of varied concentrations. The discs were dried and placed on the medium previously seeded with organisms in petri plates at suitable distance. The petri plates were stored in an incubator at 28 ± 2 °C for 24 h. The zone of inhibition thus formed around each disc containing the test compounds was measured accurately in mm. The bacteria used in these investigations included *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Bacillus thurengiensis*. Micostatin and Streptomycin were used as reference compounds for antifungal and antibacterial activities, respectively.

All the tin(IV) coordination compounds were tested against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The result shows that all the complexes were active against Gram-positive bacteria while less active against *E. coli*, which is Gram-negative.

The result further show that complexes were more active than the ligands which indicates that metallation increases the biological activity. The antifungal activity of some ligands and their corresponding tin complexes. The chelation theory³⁹⁻⁴¹ accounts for the increased activity of the metal complexes. The chelation reduces the polarity of the metal atom mainly because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and pos-

sible π electron delocalisation within a whole chelating ring⁴²⁻⁴⁴. The chelation increases the lipophilic nature of the central atom which subsequently favours its permeation through the lipid layer of the cell membrane. Fungicidal screening data and bacterial screening data results are listed in Table 6.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Strict precautions were taken to exclude atmospheric moisture while carrying out experimental work and chemical reactions. All the chemicals used in this work of AR grade and all the reactions were carried out under anhydrous and oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere. Chemicals and solvents used were dried and purified by standard methods³⁰ and moisture was excluded from the glass apparatus using CaCl_2 drying tube.

Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method and sulphur by Messenger's method³¹. The IR spectra were recorded on a FTIR spectrophotometer using Shimadzu-Japan 8400S, in the region $4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ using KBr optics. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the samples were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solutions on JEOLFT AL300 NMR spectrometer operating at 300 and 75.45 MHz, respectively.

Molar conductance measurements were made in anhydrous dimethyl formamide at 36 ± 1 °C using a model 305 Systronics conductivity bridge. Molecular weight determinations were carried out by the Rast Camphor Method³².

Synthesis of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones :

Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones were synthesized by the condensation of 4-acetyl biphenyl, 2-acetyl flurene, 9-acetyl anthracene, anthraldehyde and 4-fluoroacetophenone with semicarbazide and thiosemicarbazide in 1 : 1 molar ratio using ethanol as reaction medium.

The solution was refluxed on a water bath for 2 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature. The crystalline solids were separated out and purified by recrystallization from the same solvent. This list of ligands is given on the Table 1.

Synthesis of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn}(\text{N}^{\text{O}})]$ complexes :

These complexes were prepared by stirring $(\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn})_2\text{O}$

Table 5. ¹³C NMR spectral data of ligands and their organotin(IV) complexes

Compd.	Chemical shifts in δ ppm															
	C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6	C-7	C-8	C-9	C-10	C-11	C-12	C-13	C-14	C-15	Sn-Bu
C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	144.3	136.6	132.7	129.7	127.3	133.6	136.6	127.4	129.0	127.4	129.0	127.3	127.4	129.0	115.2	-
[(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ O)- (C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn]	163.0	130.8	126.0	129.0	128.0	143.0	143.0	128.4	129.0	126.0	129.0	128.4	128.0	129.0	126.0	41.0, 26.2, 14.3, 10.6
C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	144.6	136.6	132.7	129.7	127.3	133.6	136.6	127.4	129.0	127.4	129.0	127.3	127.4	129.0	115.2	-
[(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ S)- (C ₄ H ₉) ₃ Sn]	163.0	130.8	127.4	129.0	127.4	136.6	140.6	127.4	129.0	127.0	129.0	127.4	127.4	129.0	126.0	43.0, 26.2, 13.3, 14.6

C and H analysis are found satisfactory.

Table 6. Antimicrobial screening data of the ligands and their tin(IV) complexes

Antimicrobial activity	Compounds											Ref.
	in ppm	L ¹ H	L ² H	L ³ H	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ N ₃ OSn	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ N ₃ SSn	C ₂₈ H ₄₁ N ₃ SSn	C ₂₈ H ₄₁ N ₃ OSn	C ₂₉ H ₄₁ N ₃ SSn	C ₂₉ H ₄₁ N ₃ OSn		
Antifungal inhibition (% after 96 h (concentration 50, 100 and 200 ppm)	<i>Fusarium</i>	50	40	45	49	52	59	50	53	55	69	
		100	51	55	58	62	57	59	63	59	86	
	<i>A. flavus</i>	200	70	75	78	81	77	79	82	80	98	
		50	39	-	50	51	45	52	54	55	72	
	<i>A. niger</i>	100	50	55	59	61	57	61	64	67	82	
		200	67	73	76	79	74	77	81	84	96	
	<i>R. phaseoli</i>	50	45	49	51	53	50	53	55	54	70	
		100	58	60	63	65	62	64	66	70	91	
		200	65	69	75	77	71	75	78	81	100	
		50	46	-	52	54	-	53	55	51	71	
Antibacterial inhibition (mm) after 24 h (concentration 500 and 1000 ppm)	<i>E. coli</i> (-)	100	59	61	64	66	61	65	68	66	86	
		200	67	70	74	77	72	75	79	82	100	
	<i>Bacillus thurengiensis</i> (-)	500	8	8	10	11	10	13	17	9	1	
		1000	11	12	14	15	14	16	19	10	2	
	<i>Proteus miltamilis</i> (-)	500	9	9	12	14	12	16	16	13	3	
		1000	12	15	17	18	17	18	19	14	5	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (+)	500	12	15	16	17	15	16	18	15	15	
		1000	15	17	18	19	17	19	19	16	17	

Here reference compound is -
in Antifungal - Mycostatin, in Antibacterial - Streptomycin.

(0.001 mol) with NO donor ligand (0.002 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) solution in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about 6–8 h. After the reaction was completed, the resulting product was rendered free from the solvent and then washed repeatedly with dry cyclohexane. The products (Table 2) so formed were finally dried *in vacuo* at 40–50 °C for 3–4 h.

Synthesis of [Bu₃Sn(NS)] complexes :

These complexes were prepared by stirring (Bu₃Sn)₂O (0.001 mol) with NS donor ligand (0.002 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) solution in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about 6–8 h. After the reaction was completed, the resulting product was rendered free from the solvent and then washed repeatedly with dry cyclohexane. The products (Table 2) so formed were finally dried *in vacuo* at 40–50 °C for 3–4 h.

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